

Effect of *Centella asiatica* Extract from Tissue Culture on the Growth of *Streptococcus mutans*

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This research is a literature review between plant physiology and microbiology. Plant tissue culture is one of the sciences of plant physiology by using a technique with the aim of multiplying plants on a large scale. *Streptococcus mutans* is a bacteria that has a role in causing dental caries. By conducting plant tissue culture on *Centella asiatica* plants it is expected to get superior uniform plants so that the best secondary metabolites are obtained to inhibit the growth of *Streptococcus mutans* bacteria.

One way to produce a high and uniform secondary metabolite content is through plant tissue culture (Ling, 2004). Plant propagation with plant tissue culture is a way to get large amounts of plants in a short and sterile time (Nova, 2008). Propagation through in vitro is a method of plant propagation using organs, tissues and cells with aseptic conditions (Yusnita, 2003).

According to Winarto and Surbakti (2003), *Centella asiatica* plant has several active ingredients, namely saponin triterpenoids, genin triterpenoids, essential oils, flavonoids, phytosterols and other active ingredients. The most important active ingredients are triterpenoids and saponins which include asiaticosides, centelosides, madecosides, asiatic acid and other components. *Centella asiatica* has an antibacterial effect because it has secondary metabolites, namely saponins. According to research by J. Barnes et. al. (1996) stated that saponin derivatives, asiaticosides are lipophilic and can form complex compounds with cell membranes through hydrogen bonds, then destroying the permeability of bacterial cell walls.

Streptococcus mutans is a gram-positive, facultative anaerobic bacteria that is round, arranged like a chain and is generally found in the mouth. *Streptococcus mutans* is a group of bacteria that produces lactic acid and was first discovered in 1924 by J. Kilian Clarke (Clarke, 1924). These bacteria grow optimally at temperatures around 18-40 degrees Celsius (Nugraha, 2008). *Streptococcus mutans* is a bacteria that causes plaque on the surface of the teeth. The occurrence of this is due to the ability of *Streptococcus mutans* to use sucrose to produce a sticky extracellular product called a polysaccharide-based dextran by means of the enzyme dextransucrase (Moffatt et al, 2010)

Based on the research of Zahanis, Mansyurdin, Zozy, Amril (2014), the A. Rhizogenes strain is the best strain to induce *Centella asiatica* hair roots, and the best explants to stimulate hair roots are leaf explants. Based on research conducted by Narayanan et al (2010) by separating some of the secondary metabolites of *Centella asiatica*, namely acetone, ethyl acetate and hexane. The research was conducted by comparing its effects on several micro-organisms, one of which is *Streptococcus mutans*. The results of this study showed that the inhibitory power of acetyl and ethyl acetate was 8 mm, and the inhibitory power of hexane was 10 mm on the growth of *Streptococcus mutans*. From the description above, combining plant physiology with microbiology is expected to develop science for human needs

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